

NAA (0.5 mg/liter), 2,4-D (1.0 mg/liter), and benzyl aminopurine (0.5 mg/liter) without kinetin.

Temperature was maintained at 25 + 10 °C. Callus first appeared 22 d after inoculation.

Callus induction and development were more effective at 1,000 lx. Well-developed callus was 20% and poor callus, 66.6% when cultures were grown with light; they were 0% and 53.33% when cultures were grown in darkness,

indicating that light has some effect on callus induction. Further growth and development was measured weekly. After 8 wk in culture, the callus grew sufficiently for subculturing.

Subculturing was done in the same medium. Initially, growth was slower, with a callus doubling time of about 8 wk. But with frequent subculturing, callus doubling time was reduced to 5 wk.

Under the microscope, no *Anabaena* cells were found in mature callus cells (see figure). This indicates that *Anabaena*-free *Azolla pinnata* cultures can be produced through tissue culture of leaf explants. It could be possible to isolate *Anabaena*-free *Azolla* protoplast from these calli which could be utilized for future somatic cell fusion experiments with improved N₂-fixing *Anabaena* cells. □

Cultural practices to reduce winter damage to rice

M. Mahadevappa and Nagaraju, Seed Technology Department, Agricultural College, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, India

In the tank-fed areas of southern Karnataka India, cold temperature-sensitive rice varieties planted after the first week of Sep fail to produce any grain. The main cause is high susceptibility to low temperature at flowering. Local cold-tolerant varieties S705, S317, and Mangala fail because of heavy disease pressure. We tested postponing flowering time by cutting tillers to 10 cm at varying times after transplanting. Six varieties with varying maturities were sown 11 Sep 1985 and transplanted 10 Oct 1985.

Cutting up to 74 d after seeding (DAS) did not delay flowering because the primordia was unaffected (Table 1). Cutting 84 and 96 DAS markedly

Table 1. Effect of pruning on days to 50% flowering of winter rices. Bangalore, India, 1985.

Entry	Days to 50% flowering					
	No cutting	54 DAS	64 DAS	74 DAS	84 DAS	96 DAS
ES18	94	100	100	110	127	131
Mangala	104	110	111	113	126	131
IR19743-25-2-2	100	103	107	110	114	126
IR18476-55-2	100	104	107	110	114	127
IR15579-135-3	114	126	126	127	131	133
IR9202-25-1-3	110	117	121	124	127	131

Table 2. Effect of pruning of winter rices on tillering. Bangalore, India, 1985.

Entry	Tillers (no.)					
	No cutting	54 DAS	64 DAS	74 DAS	84 DAS	96 DAS
ES18	14	16	15	19	18	15
Mangala	16	20	39	25	14	20
IR19743-25-2-2	19	18	14	17	16	15
IR18476-55-2	14	10	8	13	11	8
IR15579-135-3	12	10	9	14	13	12
IR9202-25-1-3	15	14	11	15	12	11

delayed flowering because the stem tip was pruned. Flowering delay due to cutting date varied by genotype. 11315579-135-3 could be delayed a

maximum of 19 d, ES18 could be delayed 37 d.

Plant height and tiller production did not vary because of pruning (Table 2). □

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on rice yield

A. K. Chakraborty and B. Bhattacharya, Agriculture Department, Calcutta University, India

We studied the effect of slow-release N fertilizers on grain yield, total N uptake, and fertilizer efficiency using Ratna variety during the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons.

Soil was Gangetic alluvial clay-loam with pH 6.7, 0.35% organic C, and

Effect of slow-release urea materials on yield and fertilizer efficiency. Calcutta, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Fertilizer efficiency (%)
Control	2.0	2.9	34.28	—
Urea	2.9	3.9	58.31	24.03
Urea supergranule	3.0	3.9	60.69	26.41
Neem cake urea mixture	3.3	4.3	70.41	36.13
Lac-coated urea	3.3	4.3	77.48	43.20
Sulfur-coated urea	3.9	4.9	94.89	60.61
Bitumen-coated urea formaldehyde	3.9	4.8	93.64	59.36
Sawdust urea formaldehyde	3.7	4.6	85.76	51.48
Urea formaldehyde	3.6	4.5	84.60	49.37
Mean	3.3	4.2	70.81	43.45
SE (±)	0.66	0.69	6.82	5.13
CD (0.05)	0.37	0.37	—	—